

Development of four dissemination videos

Deliverable 7.3

Development of four dissemination videos

Deliverable 7.3

How to Cite

Leal, M.C., Marques, J., Bramley, B., Smanis, T., Urgeghe, A.M., Burrows, M., Appeltans, W., Provoost, P., Principe, S.C., Krause-Jensen, D., Lønborg, C., Graversen, A.E., Lillis, H., Stewart, E., Assis, J., Addamo, A.M., Costello, M.J. 2025. Development of four dissemination videos. Science Crunchers, *MPA Europe Project Report Deliverable 7.3*, 8 pp. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15740555>

Version: V1.0

Date of release: 30th June 2025

Instrument call: HORIZON-CL6-2021-BIODIV-01-12

Start of the project: 1st January 2023

Duration of the project: 40 months

Co-funded by
the European Union

UK Research
and Innovation

MPA Europe is co-funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe programme (Grant Agreement: 101059988). UK participants in Horizon Europe Project MPA Europe are supported by UKRI grant numbers 10067934 JNCC and 10069750 SAMS.

Views and opinions expressed are those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect that of the European Union or UK Research and Innovation. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

The report represents the most up to date status of the information. Any potential upcoming information may be considered for incorporation in future deliverables to improve the scientific knowledge.

The MPA Europe project

MPA Europe is a project co-funded by the European Union (EU) that will map a network of locations representative of biodiversity in European seas (Atlantic Exclusive Economic Zones of the EU and its neighbours, and all the Mediterranean, Baltic, and Black seas) (Figure 1).

Figure 1: MPA Europe study area

This network will indicate where to prioritise placement of Marine Protected Areas (MPA) for biodiversity protection and how Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) can maximise blue carbon benefits. By using a holistic set of biodiversity measures, from species to ecosystems (including habitats), and environmental data including carbon storage, water currents, and climate change velocity models, it will be possible to quantify and map both the present and future connectivity within the proposed MPA network. The multiple scenarios provided will support wider and improved MSP by policy makers, industry, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs). The major scientific areas of the project and its outcomes are summarized in the infographic presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. MPA Europe project scientific areas

The inter-disciplinary approach of MPA Europe is supported by a diversity of partners. These include Nord University (Norway), the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO (Belgium), the Scottish Association for Marine Science (Scotland, UK), the Centre of Marine Sciences (Portugal), the Ocean University of China (China), Science Crunchers (Portugal), the University of the Ryukyus (Japan), Aarhus University (Denmark), and the Joint Nature Conservation Committee (England, UK). The partners include experts in marine biology, taxonomy, ecology, oceanography, biogeochemistry, and biogeography, MPA network design, benthic habitat mapping, carbon dynamics, species distribution, climate modelling, and MSP compose the MPA Europe team.

Deliverable 7.3 overview

This document summarizes the procedures involved in producing Deliverable 7.3 of MPA Europe project focusing on the “Development of four dissemination videos” and their publication in the project’s YouTube channel and website.

Communicating MPA Europe for wider audiences

Why videos?

Communicating scientific research effectively to wider society requires more than publishing academic studies (Barnosky et al., 2016). Ocean literacy goes beyond knowledge alone; it involves fostering understanding of the ocean’s role in human and planetary well-being, and influencing how people relate to, value, and interact with marine environments. It relies on accessible, up-to-date communication of marine science, enabling informed attitudes and behaviours (Principle 9, Schoedinger et al., 2010). Strengthening ocean literacy can therefore support the behavioural changes needed to promote sustainable ocean stewardship (Kelly et al., 2021). In this context, MPA Europe has developed to date four short videos that translate complex project objectives and interlinks into key messages in a format accessible for a wide audience, including policy-makers, stakeholders, educators, and the general public. Videos are a powerful communication tool to bridge the gap between science and society, offering an engaging and visual medium to improve understanding of marine conservation, climate change mitigation, and sustainable ocean management.

From concept to screen: how the videos were produced

The production of each video followed a structured process:

1. **Scriptwriting** – Scripts were co-developed by MPA Europe’s science partners involved in the several work packages and the communication partner (Science Crunchers) to ensure scientific accuracy and clarity (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Excerpt of the script for “Protecting Carbon Stores in European Seas” video.

2. **Storyboarding** – After script curation and revision by all partners involved in each video, visual concepts and sequences were outlined to align the narrative with engaging graphics and imagery (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Excerpt of the storyboard for “Protecting Carbon Stores in European Seas” video.

3. **Video production** – Final videos were produced using professional animation and video editing tools, ensuring alignment with MPA Europe’s visual identity and communication objectives (see each video description and link).

Overview and short descriptions of the videos

The four videos produced so far can be found on the project’s YouTube channel (<https://www.youtube.com/@mpaeuropeproject>) (Figure 3) and website (<https://mpa-europe.eu/videos-resources/>).

Figure 3. Screenshot of the MPA Europe YouTube channel displaying the four dissemination videos included in this deliverable report.

Video 1 - [MPA Europe project](#)

This introductory video explains the aims of MPA Europe: to map the optimal locations for Marine Protected Areas across European seas, contributing to better-informed marine spatial planning (Leal et al., 2023). It supports ocean literacy by clarifying how science-based MPA networks can enhance biodiversity protection and climate resilience.

Figure 4. Screenshot of a scene in the video “What's the MPA Europe project about?”.

Video 2 - [Benefits of Marine Protected Area Networks](#)

Based on the latest MPA Europe research, this video shows how networks of MPAs provide greater benefits than isolated sites, supporting species’ life cycles, enhancing ecosystem resilience, and enabling climate adaptation (Leal et al., 2025a). It helps audiences grasp the scientific rationale for MPA network design.

Figure 5. Screenshot of a scene in the video “Benefits of Marine Protected Area Networks”.

Video 3 - [Protecting Carbon Stores in European Seas](#)

This video explores the concept of blue carbon and illustrates how well-managed MPAs help mitigate climate change by protecting carbon-rich marine habitats (Leal et al., 2025b). It raises awareness of the links between marine conservation and climate action.

Figure 6. Screenshot of a scene in the video “Protecting Carbon Stores in European Seas”.

Video 4 - [MPA Europe Map Platform Tutorial](#)

This tutorial guides viewers through the online interactive platform hosted by OBIS, where MPA Europe’s species range maps for over 10,000 marine species are displayed (Leal et al., 2024). It demonstrates how to navigate the platform, search for species, and interpret the mapped data. The video helps users—ranging from scientists and marine planners to educators and the interested public—access and use these valuable tools for understanding marine biodiversity and informing conservation decisions, thus contributing to greater ocean literacy.

Figure 7. Screenshot of a scene in the video “MPA Europe Maps Platform Tutorial”.

References

- Barnosky, A.D., Ehrlich, P.R., Hadly, E.A. (2016). Avoiding collapse: grand challenges for science and society to solve by 2050. *ELEMENTA Sci Anthr* 4:000094.
<https://doi.org/10.12952/journal.elementa.000094>
- Kelly, R., Evans, K., Alexander, K., Bettiol, S., Corney, S., Cullen-Know, C., Cvitanovic, C., de Salas, K., Emad, G.R., Fullbrook, L., Garcia, C., Ison, S., Ling, S., Macleod, C., Meyer, A., Murray, L., Murunga, M., Nash, K.L., Norris, K., Oellermann, M., Scott, J., Stark, J.S., Wood, G., Pecl, G.T. (2021). Connecting to the oceans: supporting ocean literacy and public engagement. *Reviews in Fish Biology and Fisheries* 32, 123–143.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11160-020-09625-9>
- Leal, M.C., Marques, J.F., Bramley, B., Addamo, A.M., Costello, M.J. (2025a). *Benefits of Marine Protected Area Networks*. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=y_tSFk_d61A
- Leal, M.C., Marques, J.F., Bramley, B., Smanis, T., Urgeghe, A.M., Burrows, M., Appeltans, W., Provoost, P., Principe, S.C., Krause-Jensen, D., Lønborg, C., Graversen, A.E., Lillis, H., Stewart, E., Assis, J., Campoy, A.N., Heikes-Knapton, S., Addamo, A.M., Costello, M.J. (2023). *MPA Europe Project*.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=F4iuZjWnBJ8>
- Leal, M.C., Marques, J.F., Krause-Jensen, D., Burrows, M., Lønborg, C., Bramley, B., Addamo, A.M., Costello, M.J. (2025b). *Protecting Carbon Stores in European Seas*.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ywTUITVP3lk>
- Leal, M.C., Marques, J.F., Principe, S.C., Appeltans, W., Provoost, P., Addamo, A.M., Costello, M.J. (2024). *MPA Europe Map Platform Tutorial*.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=o0DwqXiZVe8>
- Schoedinger, S., Uyen Tran, L., Whitley, L. (2010). From the principles to the scope and sequence: A brief history of the ocean literacy campaign. *NMEA Special Report #3*
<https://mare.lawrencehallofscience.org/wp-content/uploads/sites/2/2023/03/OL-From-the-Principles.pdf>

